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AN ANALYTICAL STUDY ON CSR EXPENDITURE OF BSE LISTED COMPANIES IN INDIA

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Abstract

Spending on CSR is not new in India. It has raised a lot of expectations and gained growing recognition as a new and emerging form of governance in India after legislating of CSR mandate in Companies Act, 2013, w.e.f 1st April, 2014. India has become the first country to mandate CSR through a statutory provision. Countries like U.K, U.S.A, China, Germany and Australia have voluntary guidelines for CSR spending/reporting. Others like France, Denmark, Sweden, Indonesia and Malaysia have mandatory guidelines, but they follow a specific code and all companies do not come under the purview of mandatory guidelines. There is no strong legislation, as in India, for CSR spending. Section 135 of Companies Act makes it mandatory for all the companies with turnover of Rs.1,000 crore and more or a net worth of Rs.500 crore and more or net profit of Rs.5 crore and more to spend at least two percent of their three-year average profit every year on CSR activity. If the company fails to spend such amount, the Board shall give in its report the reasons for not spending. The paper investigates the CSR spending status of BSE listed companies for the year 2014-15. Data is collected from Business Responsibility Reports and Annual Reports of BSE listed companies and also grades are given to companies based on their CSR expenditure. Thus CSR Act has made companies understand their responsibilities towards the society and act conscientiously. It has opened new opportunities for all stakeholders to devise innovative ways to contribute to equitable social and economic development.

Keywords: *CSR, Business Responsibility Reports, Companies Act 2013, Section 135, CSR Spending*

Introduction

The concept of CSR spending is not new in India. It has gained growing recognition as a new and emerging form of governance in India with the inclusion of mandatory CSR in the New Companies Act 2013, which has been enforced from 1st April 2014 in India. Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA), Government of India on February 27, 2014 has notified the rules for CSR spending u/s135 of the New Companies Act 2013 along with Companies (Corporate Social Responsibility Policy) Rules, 2014 effective from 1st April 2014.

Corporate Social Responsibility is the concept according to which the corporation has to undertake the responsibility of their activities affecting the society at large. The economic globalization resulted in a demand for corporations to play a central role in efforts to eliminate poverty, achieve equitable and accountable systems of governance and ensure environmental security. There was a need to make business a part of society and to maximize positive benefits that business endeavor can bring to human and environmental well being and to minimize the harmful effects of irresponsible business. The scheme which was developed from this concern is known as the “Corporate Social Responsibility” (Saksena, H.)

CSR has become the soul of every business in today’s competitive world and it lends a competitive edge and ensures sustainable growth. The impact of corporate activities on the environment and society has increased the importance of sustainable practices and the corporate social responsibility. The increasing pressures from various agents have made companies implement CSR activities and, consequently disclose their behavior and achievements.

Government action has become necessary to make public disclosure mandatory because government can compel disclosure from private entities, legislate performance in transparency and create disclosure requirements backed by the legitimacy of democratic processes.

With a view to provide a framework for companies (private and public) to implement need-based CSR activities, The Ministry of Corporate Affairs, Government Of India issued the National Voluntary Guidelines on Social, Environmental and Economic Responsibilities of business

(NVG SEE 2011) in July 2011 to encourage Indian inc to make voluntary disclosures on the triple bottom line in line with sustainability reporting framework of GRI.

Based on NVG SEE 2011, in August 2012, the Securities and Exchange Board of India assuming the significance on disclosure of non- financial measures and to drive transparency in the marketplace, made Business Responsibility Reporting (BRR) mandatory for the top 100 entities by market capitalization on the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and National Stock Exchange (NSE). The BRRs should be included in the annual report filings for the financial years ending on or after December 31, 2012 effectively applicable from financial year 2012-13.

There was no strong legislation, as in India, for CSR spending and spending by corporate sector was voluntary. Guidelines released in July 2011 were also voluntary in nature. The Companies Act, 2013 has detailed provisions relating to CSR making it mandatory for companies above a certain size. With this, India has become the first country to mandate CSR through a statutory provision. Countries like U.K, U.S.A, China, Germany and Australia have voluntary guidelines for CSR spending/reporting. Others like France, Denmark, Sweden, Indonesia and Malaysia have mandatory guidelines, but they follow a specific code and all companies do not come under the purview of mandatory guidelines. Section 135 of Companies Act 2013 makes it mandatory for all the companies with turnover of Rs.1,000 crore and more or a net worth of Rs.500 crore and more or net profit of Rs.5 crore and more to spend at least two percent of their three-year average profit every year on CSR activity. If the company fails to spend such amount, the Board shall give in its report the reasons for not spending.

Considering the importance and wide interest in the subject of CSR, the study aims to compare the actual CSR amount that a company spends in a financial year, after implementation of Companies Act 2013.

Evolution of CSR in India

Philanthropy in India has had a long history. In general, backdrop to philanthropy was always the religious beliefs and sentiments. CSR in a more formative way came into being during the freedom movement. Later, public sector undertakings (PSUs) were considered the main drivers

of equal distribution of wealth and socio-economic development. CSR has evolved in phases and therefore, its history and evolution in India can be studied in different phases.

PHASE 1 (1850 TO 1914)

The first phase of CSR was known for the noble acts of philanthropist's .Till 1850 CSR was influenced by family values, traditions, culture and religion, as also industrialisation. The wealth of business class was distributed with the society by setting up temples or religious institutions. In the Pre independence era, the pioneers of industrialization like Tata's, Birla's, Godrej, Bajaj's promoted the concept of CSR by setting up charitable foundations, educational and healthcare institutions, and trusts for community development. During this period social benefits were driven by political motives.

PHASE 2 (1910 TO 1960)

In the second phase, during the independence movement, Mahatma Gandhi urged rich industrialists to share their wealth and benefit the poor and backward sections of the society. Mahatma Gandhi introduced the notion of "trusteeship", which helped socio-economic growth. According to the principle of trusteeship, the industry leaders had to manage their wealth so as to benefit the common man. He influenced the industrialists and business houses to set up trusts for colleges, research centres and training institutes.

PHASE 3 (1960 TO 1980)

The third phase of CSR was characterised by the emergence of PSUs (Public Sector Undertakings) and laws relating labour and environmental standards i.e. "element of Mixed Economy" to ensure better distribution of wealth in society. The policy on industrial licensing and taxes, and restrictions on the private sector resulted in corporate malpractices which finally paved the way for the enactment of suitable legislation on corporate governance, labour and environmental issues. Since the success rate of PSUs did not prove significant there was a gradual shift in expectations from public to private sector, with the latter getting actively involved in socio-economic development. In 1965, academicians, politicians and businessmen

conducted a nationwide workshop on CSR where major stress was given to social accountability and transparency.

PHASE 4 (1980 ONWARDS)

In the fourth phase CSR became characterised as a sustainable business strategy by abandoning their traditional engagement with CSR and integrating it into a sustainable business. The wave of liberalisation, privatisation and globalisation (LPG), together with partial withdrawal of controls and licensing systems, led to a boom in the economic growth of the country. This further led to an increased momentum in industrial growth, making it possible for companies to contribute more towards social responsibility. What started as charity is now understood and accepted as responsibility.

Recent Developments of CSR in India

2009

In order to encourage Indian corporate to report on CSR issue, Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA) of the Government of India issued 'CSR Voluntary Guidelines 2009' in December 2009, effective from financial year 2009-10. These guidelines were voluntary and require business entities to formulate a CSR policy to guide its strategic planning and a roadmap for its CSR initiatives. Thus, government regulations existed but there was absence of monitoring and enforcement of these regulations on the part of government (Scott, W.R. (2004)

2011

Based on a revision of the Voluntary Guidelines, National Voluntary Guidelines for the Social, Environmental and Economic Responsibilities of Business, were launched on 8th July 2011. The 2011 Guidelines aimed to help companies use their entrepreneurship to effectively contribute to the economic and social betterment of communities by disclosing their responsible business practices based on an apply or explain approach and second, to make their operations sustainable in a manner that enables them to meet their current needs without compromising the needs of future generations. The NVGs provide nine broad-based Principles on responsible business behavior, each with recommended Core Elements. While the 2011 Guidelines identify

the areas where responsible practices need to be adopted, the accompanying Reporting Framework provides a disclosure template which can be used to report on performance in these areas. The Guidelines also provide a framework for responsible business action for Indian multinational companies planning to invest or already operating in other parts of the world.

2012

The Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI) releases a circular dated 13 August 2012, which mandates top 100 listed companies based on market capitalization listed on BSE and NSE to report their environmental, social and governance (ESG) initiatives. SEBI developed a business responsibility report (BRR) framework based on the nine principles of NVGs and required these top 100 listed companies to include the BRR within their annual reports.

2013

Release of Guidelines on Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainability for Central Public Sector Enterprises

2013 (Mandatory CSR obligations under Companies Act 2013)

Regulatory systems have potential to promote CSR implementation among organizations with stricter monitoring and enforcement. Section 135 of Companies Act 2013 prescribes that each company with a net worth of Rs.500 crore or a turnover of Rs.1,000 crore or net profit of Rs.5 crore will be required to spend a minimum of 2 % of its average net profit for the immediately preceding three financial years on CSR activities in India included in Schedule VII of the Act.

It replaces the Companies act 1956 and emphasizes carrying forward the agenda of Corporate Social Responsibility. If a company is unable to meet 2% clause of CSR spending in a year it should specify the reasons for not spending that amount in its Director's Report published in the annual report. One of the major drawbacks in the provisions which may affect the efficiency of the CSR implementation is the fact that there is no penal provision regarding non-compliance of the provisions with respect to spending or in reporting part. However, there are apparent penal

consequences if a company fails to even set up the CSR committee or fails to create a policy etc. If a company fails to spend the money, it only has to report this along with reasons.

With the aim of formulating and monitoring the CSR policy of a company, a CSR Committee of the Board needs to be constituted. Section 135 of the 2013 Act requires the CSR Committee to consist of at least three directors, including an independent director. However, CSR Rules exempts unlisted public companies and private companies that are not required to appoint an independent director from having an independent director as a part of their CSR Committee and stipulates that the Committee for a private company and a foreign company need have a minimum of only 2 members.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Saha (2013) studied the current practices of CSR in various Indian companies. For this study, 18 companies were selected on random basis from the depository of the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI). The study concluded that the performances of the selected companies on CSR are good. Many companies however over performed whereas many couldn't perform well to that extent.

Verma et al., (2015) studied Corporate Social Responsibility expenditure of the ten largest and most powerful companies in India prior to the implementation of CSR provisions of Companies Act 2013- Studies suggest that large corporations are precursors to CSR commitments in a society and hence, mandatory CSR spending in large companies is likely to positively influence CSR in smaller companies.

B. Ramesh (2015) conducted a study to get an overview on the New CSR provision envisaged under section 135, and investigated the spending pattern of Indian companies contributing towards CSR activities.

Ramanujam & Sangeetha (2013) stated that at last, Indian Parliament found time to enact the new law for companies in India. They highlighted on the tax implications, Sooner or later, claims are bound to be made on the amounts spent on CSR as the expenditure is mandated under the law. Also what happens if companies choose to play safe and contribute to the Prime Minister's

National Relief Fund to avoid all controversies? Such contributions will also be tax deductible. They concluded that every effort should be made to see that there is no litigation in implementing the new policy. Both the corporate houses and the department of company affairs owe it to the public at large to ensure the success of the new initiative.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

With an objective to explore CSR spending in India, twenty five companies listed on Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) are taken on the basis of the availability of latest annual reports of financial year 2014-15. The study is based on secondary data, presented in tables and graphs. BSE listed companies are the largest and the most influential, establishing benchmarks for others to measure up to and also in August 2012 Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI) mandated to publish Business Responsibility Report (BRR) separately or along with their Annual Report for top 100 companies listed on BSE.

In order to analyse sector specific CSR, sample firms were grouped into five categories following Global Industrial Classification Standard (GICS). GICS is an industry taxonomy developed in 1999 by MSCI and Standard & Poor's (S&P) for use by the global financial community. It consists of 10 sectors and for the purpose of the study some sectors are clubbed and five sectors are considered for the study. For example Energy sector and Material Sector are clubbed and named as Energy and Material. The five sectors include Energy and Materials (E&M), Industrial & Consumer Discretionary (I&CD), Consumer Staple and Health Care (CS & HC), Financials & IT (F&IT) and Telecommunications and Media (TC)

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To study the CSR spending of different industrial sectors.
- To compare actual CSR spending of Twenty Five Indian Companies for the year 2014-15 after implementation of Companies Act 2013.
- To assign grades to the companies on the basis of their spending.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Table showing CSR Spending for the FY 2014-15

Name	Sector	2% of Average PAT of FY 12, 13 and 14 (in crores)	CSR Spending in FY 14- 15 (in crores)	Amount Unspent (in crores)	% Spent (average of PAT of FY 12, 13 and 14)
GAIL India	E&M	118.67	71.89	46.78	1.21
Jindal Steel & Power	E&M	47.97	49.78	Nil	2.08
JSW Steel	E&M	42.86	42.86	Nil	2
TATA Steel	E&M	168.26	171.46	Nil	2.04
Hindustan Zinc	E&M	152.64	59.28	54.65	0.78
Asian Paints	E&M	29.87	19.01	10.86	1.27
Cummins India	I&CD	15.90	8.10	7.80	1.02
Bajaj Auto	I&CD	86.33	42.91	43.42	0.99
NHPC	I&CD	47.64	47.64	Nil	2
GMR Infrastructure	I&CD	2.26	2.92	Nil	2.58
TATA Power	I&CD	29.8	31.1	Nil	2.09
NTPC	I&CD	283.48	205.18	78.3	1.45
L&T	I&CD	106.21	76.54	29.67	1.44
Adani Ports	I&CD	35.79	35.9	Nil	2.01
Adani Enterprises	I&CD	1.76	2.08	Nil	2.36
Cadila Healthcare	CS&HC	10.81	10.81	Nil	2
Colgate Palmolive	CS&HC	13.17	13.28	Nil	2.02
Dabur India	CS&HC	14.66	14.71	Nil	2.01
Hindustan Unilever	CS&HC	79.82	82.35	Nil	2.06
TCS	F&IT	285	218.42	66	1.53
HDFC Bank	F&IT	197.13	118.55	78.58	1.20
IndusInd Bank	F&IT	32.64	17.53	15.11	1.07
Kotak Mahindra	F&IT	39.20	11.97	27.23	0.61

Bank					
DLF	F&IT	12.82	12.82	Nil	2
Zee Entertainment Enterprises	TC & Media	19.3	16.8	2.5	1.74

Chart 1: Chart showing Percentage of CSR spent in FY 2014-15

The above chart shows the top spenders among the top 25 companies with the percentage of PAT spent for the year 2014-15.

From the table 1, it can be observed that out of 25 companies, only 13 companies have fulfilled the criteria of spending 2% of PAT of average of PAT of immediately preceding three financial years. Rest 12 companies have unspent amount on CSR, thus not fulfilling the criteria of prescribed expenditure. It can be seen from Table 1 and Figure 1 that among 12 companies not fulfilling the criteria, Kotak Mahindra Bank has spent least on CSR with 0.61% of average of PAT of FY 12, 13 and 14, followed by Hindustan Zinc with 0.78%, i.e not even spending 1% also.

Looking at the table, it can be seen that in terms of value, TCS has spent highest on CSR with 218.42 crores against the prescribed amount of 285 crores with 1.53%, followed by NTPC with 205.18 crores against 283.48 crores and 1.45% and then Tata Steel with 171.46 crores against 168.26 crores prescribed with 2.04%. Amongst these top three companies in terms of spending of amount, only Tata Steel which is on third position fulfilled the criteria of 2%. Adani Enterprise has spent least 2.08 crores but against 1.76 crores i.e 2.36% and spending above 2%. It can be observed from Table 1 the percentage of profits spent on CSR. The list changes its character once we look at the amount spent in absolute terms. Looking at the amount spent TCS tops the list but by percentage spent it is on 15th position and by looking at the percentage spent GMR tops the list with 2.58% with least spending of 2.92 crores on 24th position after Adani Enterprise.

In line with the study conducted on CSR Spending Estimates including Business Responsibility Report Analysis by Partners in Change- Making Corporate Social Responsibility Your Business, the companies are analysed on the basis of how much they spent on CSR in FY 14-15, keeping in mind the 2% clause which has come into effect, four grades were set. Companies that spent 2% or more than 2% of their average profits of the previous three years in FY 14-15 were categorized under Grade A; those who spent between 1 and 2% under Grade B; those who spent between 1 to .5% under Grade C and companies that spent lower than that in the last category, i.e Grade D. This can be seen from the following Table 2.

Table 2: Table showing basis of assigning grades to the companies

CSR SPENDING IN 2014-15	GRADING
2 and More than 2 % of Average Net Profit of FY 11-12, 12-13 & 13-14	A
Between 2-1% of Average Net Profit of FY 11-12, 12-13 & 13-14	B
Between 1 - .5 % of Average Net Profit of 11-12, 12-13 & 13-14	C
Less than 0.5 of Average Net Profit of FY 11-12, 12-13 & 13-14	D

Chart 2: Chart showing No. of companies in each Grade

Among the 25 companies, 13 fell under Grade A; 9 came under Grade B and only 3 in Grade C, which can be seen in Chart 2.

COMPANIES THAT SPENT MORE THAN 2% OF AVERAGE NET PROFIT OF FY 12, 13 & 14

Among the twenty five companies, Nine Companies went beyond the 2% rule and spent more than 2% of their average profits of the previous three years in 2014-15 with GMR Infrastructure

on the top with 2.58%, and four Companies spend exactly 2%. The table below shows which companies went beyond the 2% rule with percentage spent and also the grades in which they fall.

Table 3: Table showing Companies in respective Grades

Companies in Grade A	% Spent (Average of PAT of FY 12, 13 and 14)	Companies in Grade B	% Spent (Average of PAT of FY 12, 13 and 14)	Companies in Grade C	% Spent (Average of PAT of FY 12, 13 and 14)
GMR Infrastructure	2.58	Zee Entertainment Enterprises	1.74	Bajaj Auto	0.99
Adani Enterprises	2.36	TCS	1.53	Hindustan Zinc	0.78
TATA Power	2.09	NTPC	1.45	Kotak Mahindra Bank	0.61
Jindal Steel & Power	2.08	L&T	1.44		
Hindustan Unilever	2.06	Asian Paints	1.27		
TATA Steel	2.04	GAIL India	1.21		
Colgate Palmolive	2.02	HDFC Bank	1.20		
Adani Ports	2.01	IndusInd Bank	1.07		
Dabur India	2.01	Cummins India	1.02		
JSW Steel	2				
Cadila Healthcare	2				
NHPC	2				
DLF	2				

Sector Wise Analysis

Table 4: Table showing no. of companies in various sectors

Sectors	No. of companies
Energy & Material (E&M)	6
Industrial and Consumer Discretionary (I&CD)	9
Consumer Staple and Health Care (CS& HC)	4
Financials & IT (F&IT)	5
Telecommunications & Media (TC)	1

From the table 1 and table 3, it can be said that companies fulfilling the criteria of 2% and more are from various sectors. No sector specific changes have been seen except for Financial and IT companies which have not fulfilled the criteria and their spending on CSR falls in Grade B or Grade C. In Financials and IT sector only 1 out of 5 has fulfilled the criteria of CSR spending. For Industrial and Consumer Discretionary, 5 out of 9 companies, for Energy and Materials, 3 out of 6, for consumer staple and healthcare all the 4 companies have fulfilled the condition of 2% spend on CSR. Zee Entertainment Enterprise the only company in Telecommunications and Media sector has not fulfilled the criteria with 1.74% spend of PAT of immediately 3 preceding years of 2014-15.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The present study has analyzed CSR activities of twenty five companies in India. This study was limited in nature as annual reports for FY 2014-15 for all the companies were not available. Future research can consider larger number of companies to assess CSR and also relation between the size of the company with CSR spending can be done. The study concludes that 13 out of 25 companies studied have spent 2% or more than 2% of PAT of FY 12, 13 and 14. So it can be said that although CSR spend has become mandatory, all the companies are not fulfilling the criteria. In some cases, companies do not even spend 1% of their PAT on CSR. Also there is no penalty for the companies not spending 2%, if they don't meet the 2% average spending; they

will have to give an explanation only. Also nothing is mentioned in the Act for the companies not falling in purview of this mandatory clause of Section 135 of Companies Act 2013. Therefore Government can align CSR provisions with income-tax laws and make appropriate changes which are currently not included to increase the recognition for CSR and to promote and give momentum to CSR. Also companies need to constitute a CSR Committee by assessing and measuring the gap between the actual and ought to be spent amount on CSR

REFERENCES

- B. Ramesh & S. Mendes (2015). Corporate Social Responsibility– Perspectives in Indian Context. Australian Journal of Business and Economic Studies, Volume 1 No. 2 September 2015
- D.Rajasekar, and T. Antony. (2015). Analysis of the Amount Spent For Corporate Social Responsibility Activities by the Maharatna Public Sector Undertakings. International Journal In Management And Social Science, Vol.03 Issue-01, (January 2015)
- H. Verma, Selvalakshmi. M, and N. Jain (2015). CSR Stipulations of Companies Act, 2013 and Actual CSR Expenditure by Top Indian Companies Prior To Its Implementation: A Comparative Study. International Journal of Science Technology & Management, Vol. No.04, Special Issue No.02, February 2015, 113-121
- KPMG in India, India Corporate Responsibility Reporting Survey 2013, December 2013
- Partners in Change- Making Corporate Social Responsibility your Business, “SECTION 135 (The NEW COMPANIES ACT 2013) CSR SPENDING ESTIMATES - BSE TOP 100 (Including Business Responsibility Reports Analysis)”
- P.Athma, and N.Yarragorla. CSR Guidelines: CPSE Vs Companies Act 2013(A case study of Maharatna Companies)
- Saha Anandaraj (2013), CSR Practices of select Indian Companies – A Descriptive Study of the Quantitative and Qualitative Aspects of Disclosures, The Management Accountant, Vol. 48, No. 6, pp. 651 – 659.
- Saksena, H. “Corporate social responsibility of financial institutions: An Indian perspective”
- Scott, W. R. (2004). “Institutional theory” p. 408-14 in Encyclopedia of Social Theory, George Ritzer, ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Socio Research & Reform Foundation (NGO) (2013), “India CSR Report”- Based on analysis of CSR Programmes of 100 Top Companies
- TCA Ramanujam & TCA Sangeetha (2013), Corporate Social Responsibilities, The Management Accountant, Vol. 48, No. 9, pp. 1068 – 1069.